

SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY GRADES

Abdullayev Parviz Asadulla o'g'li

TerDU Faculty of Social Sciences, of elementary education,
3rd grade student

Abdullayev_Parviz@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7663095>

Annotation: This article examines the issues of effectiveness in teaching the Uzbek language. When presenting each section, the features of teaching the Uzbek language are briefly and easily disclosed, special attention is focused on the most difficult problems

Key words: Uzbek language, methodology, teaching, efficiency, science

The methodology of teaching the Uzbek language is among the pedagogical sciences. It can be called applied science, since it, based on theory, is designed to solve the practical problems of education, training and development of students. Like any other science, the methodology of the Uzbek language has its own subject.

The subject of its study is the process of mastering the native language in the learning environment (mastering speech, writing, reading, grammar, phonetics, etc.). The methodology of the Uzbek language is designed to study the patterns of the formation of skills in the field of language, the assimilation of systems of scientific concepts in grammar and in other sections of the science of language.

The results of this study form the fundamental basis for solving problems: on the basis of the known patterns, it is necessary to develop an optimal system of language teaching. This system (or, rather, these systems) should provide each student with the necessary minimum of skills and knowledge of the language.

At the same time, the methodology takes into account a number of social requirements for teaching: it provides such a structure of teaching that would maximally contribute to the communist education of students, the development of their thinking, and would also be effective, fairly economical. By tradition, speaking about the tasks of the methodology as an applied science, they call its three tasks: What to teach? The answer to this question is the development of the content of education - programs in the Uzbek language, the creation of textbooks and various teaching aids for students, their continuous improvement, checking the availability and effectiveness. How to teach? In accordance with this question, teaching methods, methodological techniques, systems of exercises, recommendations for the use of certain types of assignments, manuals, sequential systems of practical work of students, lessons and their cycles, etc. are being developed. Why so and not otherwise? This implies a study of the comparative effectiveness of methods, justification of the choice of a method, experimental verification of recommendations, etc.

The methodology of the Uzbek language studies the levels of knowledge, skills and abilities of students at different stages of education, finds out the reasons for success or failure in learning, examines typical mistakes - speech, spelling, etc., finds ways to eliminate and prevent them.

Time suggests its tasks to methodology, as well as to pedagogical science as a whole. So, today in the methodology of the Uzbek language there is an active search for such methods and techniques that would ensure maximum cognitive activity and independence of schoolchildren in the educational process; the best development of students' thinking and speech; the strength of the acquired knowledge, abilities and skills, etc.

Language teaching takes place in preschool institutions, in primary and secondary schools, in technical schools (for example, in pedagogical schools), in universities. The tasks of teaching the native language at all these levels of education, of course, cannot be the same.

But the basic requirements of science are the same: everywhere the subject of science is the process of mastering a language, regardless of the level of education, the methodology studies the objective laws of mastering a language, develops training systems, tests them, etc. But each step has its own characteristics.

So, the methodology of preschool education is oriented in the field of the native language mainly on the development of the speech of children. The methodology of primary education - the Uzbek language, which interests us first of all, has its own specific features. In all its sections (except for the development of students' speech), she cannot rely, with rare exceptions, on some foundation laid earlier.

This is the reason for its very name - "methodology of primary education." Let's name the main sections of the method: "Methods of teaching literacy", ie, elementary reading and writing. The problem of teaching children to read and write has always been extremely acute not only in pedagogy, but also in social life, since the literacy of the people is their weapon in the struggle for liberation, for political consciousness, for culture. The enormous successes of the method of teaching literacy in the USSR are generally recognized. "Reading technique".

The task of the "Reading" subject in primary grades, as you know, is, first of all, to equip children with the skill of sufficiently fluent, correct, conscious and expressive reading. Primary school is designed to prepare the student for the transition to the middle school, both as a reader and as a reader. "The technique of grammar and spelling." It includes teaching elementary writing and calligraphy, the formation of grammatical concepts, the first spelling skills - when there is still no sufficient grammatical basis. "The development of students' speech."

This section is unique in elementary school. For the first time, children become aware of language, speech as a subject of study - analysis and synthesis; they master speech, which is caused not by the situation itself, but by an act of will: they are placed in conditions when they need to think over, plan, talk not only about what they really want to say, not only about what is interesting; they master written speech, which, as you know, differs from oral not only in its graphic form, but also in vocabulary, syntax, and morphological forms.

The technique should also ensure the further enrichment of the children's vocabulary, the development of their syntax, their coherent speech. The methodology of the Uzbek language, like other pedagogical sciences, affects the interests of tens, hundreds of millions of people. It is known how much grief a "deuce" brings for a dictation, for an essay.

References:

1. Ramzaeva T.G., Lvov M.R. Methods of teaching the Uzbek language in primary grades: Textbook. manual for ped students. in-tov on specials. № 2121 "Pedagogy and methodology early. training "- M .: Education, 1979. - 431 p., ill.
2. http://pedlib.ru/Books/4/0033/4_0033-1.shtml#book_page_top
3. <https://www.rki-site.ru/russkij-yazyik-kak-inostrannyij.html>